

IoT based Smart Washroom

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Abstract:

With the developments in the world of Internet of Things and its widespread use around the world, it has improved the quality of life and made it easier for customers by connecting things to the Internet to provide ease of control. And here in this project, we are trying to keep pace with the times by implementing some IoT services to manage the environment on our university campus. The project is trying to update some of the washroom features that will keep the user safe and also make the washrooms easier to use. It boils down to the automatic notification of the cleaner/in-charge when the time comes for that through an application used to deliver notifications to the cleaner. Also through the use of LED light to reduce congestion in front of the bathrooms, by turning on the LED light when the door opening movement is sensed keeping the place smelling nice by using the exhaust fans that are turned on automatically or when the LED light is turned on, the fan will also be turned on at the same time or managed by applying the cleaner to clean the smells of the place, and the automatic door to avoid touching through automatic operation through the motor and also by controlling the main door from the detergent application during the cleaning time and finally sending a notification to the cleaning worker when the wipes are finished.

Keywords: IoT , Smart washrooms, Sensors, Automatic, LED, exhaust fan, Tissue Dispenser, motor, IR sensor, motion sensor, ammonia sensor